

Who returns? Understanding experiences of graduate return to rural island communities

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ABSTRACT

High levels of out-migration of young people from rural and island communities has provoked significant concern around experiences of “brain drain”. However, recent research has shown that many young people who leave rural communities hold intentions or aspirations to return to their communities in the future. Although research has identified intentions to return in young people leaving rural communities, and has identified patterns of return in older migrants, the experience of young returnees, and specifically young graduates has received very little attention. This paper seeks to address this gap by exploring the phenomenon of return migration to the Scottish islands of Orkney and Shetland by recent graduates (within a year of graduation). Where previous research has identified the importance of employment and relationships in return migration, the findings from this project identify that it is how the dynamics of career and relationships interweave over time that creates specific spatial horizons. Drawing out the findings into a typology of graduate returners, this paper indicates the variety of experiences of graduate return and identifies a potential need for greater support of some graduate returners.

1. Introduction

The outmigration of young people is a longstanding concern in rural and island communities where a shortage of young people can be seen to threaten population and economic sustainability (Connell, 2018; Corbett, 2007; Riethmuller et al., 2021; Terman, 2020). Although youth migration from rural areas is often understood to be a result of constrained economic and educational opportunities, research has suggested this presents a rather simplistic picture. In fact, evidence shows that youth outmigration is often more clearly associated with entry to higher education than with employment opportunities (Drozdowski, 2008; Stockdale, 2002b). This suggests that it is important to understand youth out migration in relation to Higher Education transition specifically, including asking what happens for rural students *after* completing a degree.

Existing research into young people and rural migration has largely focused on the transitions of rural young people from school rather than asking about what happens after graduation. This literature has described the interrelation of educational progression and youth

outmigration as a process by which rural young people “learn to leave” their communities (Corbett, 2007). Traditions of higher education premised on residential mobility, have also been shown to make leaving home to enter higher education seem like common sense (Holdsworth, 2009). In rural communities, traditions of youth outmigration for educational progression can result in leaving becoming associated with “success” so that the process of leaving itself is valued, and staying potentially becomes stigmatised, associated with failure (Easthope and Gabriel, 2008; Haartsen and Thissen, 2014; Hayfield, 2017).

However, research has suggested that mobility may be associated with the particular life-stage of young adulthood, aligned with the “metrocentricity” (Farrugia, 2014), or the “urban ethos” (Bæck, 2004) of youth. For young people from rural areas, urban locations can appeal because they allow greater anonymity and opportunities for experimentation (Bjarnason and Thorlindsson, 2006; Hayfield, 2017). Moving to an urban area is therefore often linked to self-development and transition into adulthood (Mærsk et al., 2021). This raises the possibility that out-migration may in some cases be temporary and be followed by later return migration. Indeed, research into young rural outmigrants

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has shown that rural leavers often harbour interests in later return (Hayfield, 2017). Whether or not young people return however is a different question, especially as evidence shows that migration intentions do not always translate into actual destinations (Stockdale and Haartsen, 2018). A key limitation in the existing literature is that it has tended to explore intended migration pathways of young school leavers (Haartsen and Thissen, 2014) rather than exploring actual migration trajectories of rural young people. This is significant because it is possible that processes of socialisation into urban environments may result in changing migration intentions and young people remaining in urban communities (Riethmuller et al., 2021).

This paper seeks to explore the migration trajectories of graduates from two rural communities (the Scottish islands of Orkney and Shetland) in the year after graduation. Rural graduates are an under-researched group (Terman, 2020) and although there is a small amount of literature that explores graduate returners to small communities (e.g. Crescenzi et al., 2017; Rérat, 2014a; Terman, 2020) typically this research involves graduates across a wide range of ages. Rérat's (2014a, 2014b) research for example includes graduates from six months to ten years post-graduation. And Haartsen and Thissen's (2014) research, focused on 17–29 year olds and did not exclusively focus on graduate returnees. This paper therefore makes a significant contribution to the literature by focusing on rural graduate trajectories within the period immediately after graduation. Through exploring recent graduate pathways, the research also offers important insights into the needs of rural graduates, and draws out implications for regions seeking to make the most of the graduates as a potential source of human capital.

The rest of the paper proceeds through a number of steps. Firstly a review of the literature is offered, exploring both the literature on rural return migration, and graduate migration. The theoretical framework for the project is then introduced, before an overview of the research design and methods is given. The findings are presented, including a typology of rural return graduates, and then key points are drawn out in the discussion.

1.1. Rural return migration

The literature on rural return migration has typically had a broad focus – looking at return patterns across the life-course rather than just at the point of graduation. This literature has identified a strong sense of belonging as a potential reason why some rural leavers may wish to return (Silva et al., 2021), and has problematised the common assumption that rural leavers are less “attached” to their rural areas than rural stayers. Indeed, some evidence has suggested that a sense of belonging may even be stronger for some rural leavers than for rural stayers, and that many leavers retain strong connections to their home communities (Evans, 2016; Jamieson, 2000; Pedersen, 2018). It is perhaps unsurprising then that the evidence shows that rural leavers frequently aspire to returning to their home communities (or other rural communities) in the future (Hayfield, 2017; Lundqvist, 2019). Researchers have even suggested that by retaining very strong connections to home communities, some leavers in fact could be said to never leave at all (Haartsen and Thissen, 2014).

The evidence suggests that future returns are often anticipated at certain points in life, particularly at the point of settling down and having children (Ní Laoire, 2008; Saar and Saar, 2020; Tyrrell and Kraftl, 2015). Where rural areas are often associated with safety and security this potentially supports patterns of rotational mobility – with safety and security highly valued in early childhood, but experienced as a restriction in young adulthood (Pedersen and Gram, 2018) and then becoming positive again at the point of raising children (Crow, 2010; Hayfield, 2017; Ní Laoire, 2008). Although return to rural communities is particularly associated with raising children, other relational dynamics have also been identified as important – for example relationship breakdowns and divorce, or ageing family members (Ní Laoire, 2008).

Alongside relational dynamics, research has commonly identified

employment dynamics as important in return migration decisions (Crescenzi et al., 2017; Haartsen and Thissen, 2014; Rérat, 2014a; Riethmuller et al., 2021). Rérat (2014b) for example identifies three different trajectories for rural return, identifying how these interweave, with two trajectories being the socio familial trajectory (including gender, relationship status, partner's characteristics, whether they are a parent, and family background), and professional trajectory (field of study, field of work, kind of degree). Rérat's (2014b) third trajectory is “migration trajectory” which includes previous mobilities, region of origin, parental mobilities and location of higher education institution attended. This latter trajectory helps to identify how specific spatial location is important in intentions to return with variations apparent across rural communities (Bjarnason and Thorlindsson, 2006; Evans, 2016).

Like Rérat, Haartsen and Thissen (2014) also categorise a set of motivations for return migration, broadly combining relational and employment motivations: the social, family, functional and partner orientations. Here the “functional” motivation is work-related and these individuals are typically in careers such as “teacher, lawyer, municipal officer and medical doctor” (p.98). This finding is significant because of the evidence that in small rural and island communities, key professional roles in the community may require specific qualifications and experience that can only be gained elsewhere (Cooke and Petersen, 2019), and that in some of these professional roles, rural employment may actually offer positive opportunities for professional specialism and development (Riethmuller et al., 2021). As such it is possible that some young people may choose to make strategic educational choices, pursuing educational options elsewhere that may enable them to later return to their communities, following a strategy of “planned return” (Alexander, 2015; Rosvall and Rönnlund, 2019). Indeed, there is evidence that patterns of return and in-migration may be associated with certain public sector vocations, especially in healthcare and education, two sectors where professional level work is commonly available in rural communities (Bjarnason and Edvardsson, 2017; Cooke and Petersen, 2019; Corcoran et al., 2010; Rérat, 2014a). Rérat (2014a) for example finds that teaching is a particularly important career pathway for individuals who want to return to a specific rural community in Switzerland.

The existing literature on rural return migration literature therefore has identified a number of themes in return migration including spatial belonging, relationships and career pathways. However, the majority of research has taken place with those who are yet to leave, or those who have returned, and there is a notable gap in the literature relating to the pathways of recent graduates. This is important because transition from university is often not straightforward and the experiences of graduates in the first years after graduation have an important role in shaping longer term futures (Purcell and Elias, 2004). Understanding this post-graduation experience therefore should help to understand why some young people return and others do not, and whether, how and why intentions to return might change over time.

1.2. Graduate migration

To understand the phenomenon of graduate return migration to rural and island communities, the literature around graduate migration more generally provides important context. Here it is notable that graduate mobility in the UK is a great deal more constrained than may be commonly assumed, with only a minority of graduates (approximately 18% in 2016) moving to new regions six months after graduation (Ball, 2019). Rather graduates show marked preferences for returning to their home regions or remaining in their regions of study (Ball, 2019). Further, the evidence suggests that patterns of return migration may be increasing, with young people increasingly frequently moving back to parental homes in the first years after graduation (Sage et al., 2013).

However, mobilities are complex, with young graduates typically moving several times (Sage et al., 2013). Terminology such as

“boomerang” generation has been coined to explain the tendency of young people to return home after graduation, and the “double boomerang” where individuals return to the family home on a number of occasions (Sage et al., 2013 see also Haartsen and Thissen, 2014). High housing costs, and high instability in both housing situations and workplace transitions have been articulated as potential reasons for this pattern of graduate mobility (Hoolachan et al., 2017; Sage et al., 2013). Within this context, the family home can provide an important ‘safety net’ (Sage et al., 2013, p. 738) offering secure and low-cost accommodation. However, relational and emotional experiences also shape graduate mobility decisions (Finn, 2016; Sage et al., 2013) and families are an important source of emotional and social support (Finn, 2016).

In understanding graduate trajectories it is also important to consider evidence around inequalities. The most mobile graduates for instance are likely to have previously moved away for university and have higher levels of human capital (based on grades and institutional reputation) (Faggian et al., 2007b). Age, gender, social-class and ethnicity have also been found to impact on the mobility of graduates (Bond et al., 2008; Faggian et al., 2006, 2007a). Migration pathways are also associated with employment pathways, although the direction of cause and effect is difficult to discern. Within the UK for example the evidence shows that graduates who return to their home regions are the least likely to be in professional employment (Ball, 2015; Bond et al., 2008) whereas the most mobile graduates are the most likely to be in professional employment (Ball, 2015). As well as employment status, there is some indication that the subject of study may be important in migration trajectory, with, for example, science and social science graduates being more migratory than arts graduates (Faggian et al., 2007b).

The graduate migration literature therefore raises key questions in relation to rural return graduate migration – for example, if complexity and instability mark early graduate experiences, what impact does this have on young people who have family homes in rural, especially remote rural, locations? And, how might issues of inequality relate to rural graduate return migration?

2. Theoretical framework

This paper takes a perspective on graduate transition informed by Hodkinson and Sparkes’ (1997) careership theory. Careership theory draws from Bourdieusian sociology, especially notions of habitus, field and capital, and offers a way of understanding how career pathways develop over time through an interaction of individuals with their contexts. Taking a spatial perspective on careership theory, the notion of habitus (a form of socialised subjectivity) is valuable especially in the connections to concepts of spatial belonging, with some scholars making a direct link between the terms (Thomas, 2015; Turner, 2020). Spatial belonging in the literature is often understood as a combination of belonging to physical space (often through day to day activities) and belonging to social space including the relationships with people in a community (Cuervo and Wyn, 2017). Within an educational or career studies focus, belonging may also include professional or career belonging, sometimes understood as vocational habitus (Colley et al., 2003). Thus, utilising careership theory it is possible to see how individuals may experience different dimensions of ‘belonging’ that include career, relationships and places – and how these may influence future trajectories (Alexander, 2022). Alongside habitus, Bourdieu’s notion of capital, as utilised in careership theory highlights how individuals have different levels of resource (economic or otherwise) that act to facilitate or constrain possibilities, including mobility possibilities. As such the theoretical approach both explores how context can shape aspirations (through habitus), as well as providing constraints on choices that stem from our resources (capitals) and where we live (Alexander, 2022). Further, as careership theory considers how ideas change over time, the perspective enables an understanding both of how individuals develop career intentions (in relation to staying or leaving

rural places) and how these career intentions evolve over time (and whether or not they lead to returning).

3. Methodology

This paper presents data drawn from a larger research project exploring the career and migration trajectories of young students from the Scottish islands of Orkney and Shetland. The data presented in this paper focuses on how young students and recent graduates conceptualise and experience rural return.

3.1. Geographic context

The islands of Orkney and Shetland are located off the North coast of Scotland with each island group consisting of approximately 15–20 inhabited islands, with approximately 21–24,000 people living in each island group. The Scottish Urban-Rural classification system (Scottish Government, 2018) identifies that the entire population of the islands can be classified as living in remote small towns (34% in Orkney, 29.6% in Shetland) or remote rural communities (66% in Orkney, 70.4% in Shetland). Transport connections to the Scottish mainland are available by ferry or plane, but practically it is not possible to commute from the islands on a regular basis. As with other island communities then, staying and leaving decisions can be accentuated (Cooke and Petersen, 2019).

Although there is some Higher Education provision in the islands from the University of the Highlands and Islands (UHI) as well as distance learning options, statistical evidence shows that majority of students leave the islands to pursue higher education study. Over a five year period (2008/9–2012/13) only 6% of graduates who were domiciled in the islands prior to entering higher education graduated from UHI (Alexander, 2015). Further, statistics show that by six months after graduation relatively a very high proportion of graduates are back in (or remain) in the islands after graduation – with 39% of those whose location is known being in the islands (*ibid*).

3.2. Research design and methods

The research primarily utilised longitudinal qualitative interviewing (LQI) (Hermanowicz, 2013) with a small group of higher education students who had originally been domiciled in Orkney or Shetland prior to entering higher education. As a research method LQI is well suited to exploring process and causality in the development of individual lives (Hermanowicz, 2013; Thomson, 2007). Specifically, rather than offering insights into anticipated mobilities, or post-hoc rationalisations of mobility, it provides insights into the *process* of decisions to return or not – the “black box” in Crescenzi et al.’s words (2017).

Participants were recruited through an initial survey targeted at individuals who had been domiciled in Orkney or Shetland prior to entering Higher Education, who were studying for a full-time first-degree and due to graduate in 2015. The survey was circulated via social media, articles in the local press and on the local radio stations, and, where possible via university careers services. 86 valid responses were collected and 39 participants volunteered for further interviews. Given the relatively small number of volunteers, all of these were contacted, and from this group 23 students agreed to take part in interviews, with one later withdrawing. The sample included individuals studying at institutions across Scotland with one studying in England, and two studying at a campus of UHI in Orkney or Shetland. The sample was notably gendered with 18 out of 22 participants being women, and all were under 25 years old at the point of graduation.

Interviews were conducted over the telephone at the point of graduation (spring 2015) and one year later. Each interview contained three main questions focusing on participants’ past and present experiences and future hopes or plans. The use of comparable interview schedules at the two interview points allowed for an exploration of how career and

migration ideas had changed over time (Hermanowicz, 2013). Alongside the interviews, data was collected and analysed from the initial survey, a survey carried out six months after graduation, and a wider analysis of statistical data sets for school leavers and graduates from the islands.

3.3. Data analysis

Data from the interviews was transcribed and analysed using an approach that drew from Grounded Theory (Charmaz, 2014). In line with Grounded Theory approaches, the analytic approach was avowedly theoretical from the start, and proceeded through a process of initial coding followed by focused coding and categorisation to build theory (Charmaz, 2014). Data collection and analysis was also iterative, with the first interviews coded and analysed before the second interviews (one year later) were conducted. However, some adjustments to traditional grounded theory approaches were made, so for example, between interviews in each round, interview notes and memos were collated, but the timescales within each phase of interviewing did not allow individual interviews to be analysed before further data was collected. This also limited the possibility to engage in theoretical sampling. A further adjustment to traditional grounded theory, was that data analysis was not entirely inductive, instead the research was informed by critical realist approaches to grounded theory, which recognise that pre-existing theory as an important component of research design, data collection and analysis and therefore analysis follows a logic closer to retroduction (Kempster and Parry, 2014; Zachariadis et al., 2013).

3.4. Ethics and data presentation

Ethical approval for the project was granted by the university ethics panel. Key ethical considerations in this project focused on ethics of research in small communities where individuals may be relatively easier to identify (Damianakis and Woodford, 2012; Ellis, 2007). Although often researchers choose to obscure the location of the research to provide anonymity to participants (Damianakis and Woodford, 2012), this can act to “wash [...] out” the particularities of a place, which can be problematic in research with an explicitly spatial focus (Reid, 2017, p. 92). Additionally anonymising the location is not necessarily sufficient to allow participant anonymity especially because in small communities it is important to consider issues of ‘internal confidentiality’ (Wiles, 2013) – participants being recognisable to other participants for example. Therefore, in this project, the location has been made explicit, while significant care has been applied to removing or anonymising any potentially identifying information about participants. This includes limiting details of specific pathways (which could make participants identifiable) and not using pseudonyms (which can risk inadvertently identifying participants as it is possible to track individual responses across a publication or publications) (Damianakis and Woodford, 2012).

4. Findings

The analysis generated a theory of graduate transition in relation to place that built upon the theoretical framework outlined in section 2. The full model has been presented in more detail in a previous publication (Alexander, 2022), however this paper focuses specifically on exploring the data generated in this project relating to return migration. The findings start with an overview of return migration intentions and spatial belonging, followed by an exploration of the role of career frameworks and relational frameworks in the specific ways that pathways develop. A typology of rural graduate return migrants is then offered.

4.1. Return and belonging

Return for the graduates in this project was not an exception. The majority identified that they either would like to return in the future or that they could imagine circumstances where they might want to return. One year after graduation eight (or 36%) of the original 22 remained in, or had returned to, the islands. In line with other research, this desire was most commonly articulated in relation to wanting to return to the islands to “settle down”. This was strongly associated with having children:

I mean growing up here myself it is a great place to grow up, it is safe and like I say all my family's around, they'd have their grandparents around or whatever like I always did when I was younger.

As this quotation identifies, having family in the islands was often considered a key attraction at the point of having children. Similarly, the notion of ‘smallness’ especially in relation to safety is very commonly articulated as a reason for return especially at the point of having children.

In thinking about return, a sense of belonging to the islands is important, and is sometimes reinforced by experiences of going away, especially the un-familiarities students encounter. These unfamiliarities include for example, experiences of urban transport systems, being in ‘bigger’ settings with different opportunities, experiences of feeling different (including other people being curious about their background or accents being misunderstood), and different day-to-day lives (for a further discussion see Alexander, 2021). One student for example, offers the following example of a feeling of ‘unbelonging’ in a city compared to a rural area:

I would often find when I lived in the city and if it was a bonny day, I would want to be outside, but there's a limit to what you can do I always wanted to do stuff [outside]. It has been something I've done all my life – it is just on a weekend you go out and work outside and even potter about or, well there's always jobs to be done [on the farm].

A sense of spatial belonging therefore appears layered (Cuervo and Wyn, 2017) and includes family histories, family relationships, language (including accent and dialect), and day-to-day activities.

Importantly, though, ‘belonging’ is not a singular or a static experience. Graduates often identify that they are happy being in ‘unfamiliar’ environments while they are younger for the opportunities they provide, and then later returning to a space which feels more comfortable.

I think I'd like more stability later on in life, but right now, I don't know what I want, and you'll never know if you don't have a look around, so that's what I plan to do.

Further, as students settle into their urban lives, and as their home environments change, ‘belonging’ can become complex – with students feeling ‘at home’ in both environments. In some cases this leads to a revision of mobility intention, for example students who intended to return to the islands sometimes start to foresee futures in other locations, for many these alternative futures centre on other rural locations:

I never thought I'd actually like to live anywhere except for [the islands] I thought that would just have been horrible but now I actually could see myself living on mainland Scotland, in [rural Scottish location] so ...

In line with previous research, this demonstrates how stay and leave decisions are made and revisited over time (Stockdale and Haartsen, 2018).

4.2. Frameworks for return

However, whether or not young people envisage a return to the islands is not just dependent on spatial belonging, but on wider

experiences. Positive experiences of return are typically understood to be dependent on having a partner in the island or willing to move to the islands, and on having “good enough” employment:

That would be the ideal, to find something work wise that I wanted to do at the right time in [the islands] when I'd had enough experience of the outside world, and then move back and start a family.

The notion of ‘the right time’ is important here – with graduates imagining future points in time when spatial, career and relational goals are aligned and provide the opportunities for return. However, the challenge for many is how to manage the dynamics of career and relationships over time in order to allow for the possibility of return. Indeed, even directly after graduation, graduates describe how their spatial choices are influenced by the frameworks of their career pathway and their relationships, creating different spatial possibilities and experiences of migration, these frameworks are explored in more depth below.

4.2.1. Career frameworks

Career frameworks are a key influence on graduates’ trajectories. Graduates differ in how focused they are on specific career routes, and the subjects they have studied also open quite different employment potentials.

In this research, three different graduate career trajectories were identified: vocational trajectories (e.g. those who had studied for degrees that provided a qualification for entry into a specific vocation, such as a degree in nursing, or education), graduate trajectories (e.g. those who had entered “graduate” roles, typically in large multinational employers), and those “working their way up” (e.g. seeking to develop a career through a mix of additional experience and training). These classifications are relatively crude, and it is important to recognise that university courses vary in terms of *degree* of vocationality (Purcell et al., 2009), and that definitions of “graduate roles” are challenging, and change over time (Elias and Purcell, 2013). However, broadly, the evidence from this research highlights how different graduate career trajectories result in quite different spatial horizons.

Graduates who were “working their way up” for example typically faced unstable or low paid employment prospects, and some graduates in this category did not have a clear career direction. Without access to stable employment and a reasonable salary then moving back to the family home straight after graduation made sense:

Well, my rent is up ... so it gives me little option what to do, because if I don't have a job to go into or a place to move to, it kind of seems silly not to move home to work for a bit and save money ...

A buoyant labour market in the islands for part time and seasonal work supported these decisions. However, on return, these graduates often described significant challenges in being able to “work their way up” because of their rural location and limited access to opportunities, as well as limited ability to move.

[Other graduates] do their unpaid four week internship and that's really good experience but for me that would be like, right I've got to pay rent, find somewhere to live, potentially for just a month, it's going to be unpaid, so where does the money come from? ... you can feel a little bit like ‘oh’, like sometimes you just wish that you were down here [on the Scottish mainland]

In contrast to those “working their way up”, other graduates following much clearer career trajectories typically described limited ability to choose their locations, and often felt they had no choice but to remain away from their communities if the right roles were not available. This is the case for those in professions in healthcare or education where graduates need to enter specific kinds of role that allow them to maintain their registrations or continue with their professional training:

[After my degree] I need to do a period of training, which when I first moved away they were taking on trainees at home, but unfortunately they're not doing that any more.

The experience of this graduate (being unable to return home) is in marked contrast to that of the previous graduate (being unable to remain away) and demonstrates the significance of specific career pathway in relation to graduate migration experiences.

For some students following professional routes, migration intentions had changed over the course of their studies. A key appeal of professional routes in healthcare and education for undergraduate students is that these routes were perceived as potentially leading back to their rural communities. However, by the point of graduation a number of students pursuing these careers describe wanting to delay their return. There are two primary reasons for this, the first is to take on additional experience in their field (often specialist experience) that is only available in larger communities. The second is that they describe wanting to develop higher confidence in their profession before returning to pressurised island environments.

You can do more specialist stuff down here, rather than at home

I was like, do you know, I don't want that [to return home] when I'm still quite young and unestablished, I kind of want to feel a bit more happy with everything before I go back into this really intense environment of everybody knows me

There is, perhaps, a level of irony here that often those who were clearest about wanting to return home at the point of entry to higher education often focused on vocational routes leading to professional jobs they could undertake in the islands. However, after leaving to progress with studies in these subjects, many found that they could not, or no longer wanted to, return immediately after graduation.

Although some graduates felt they couldn't return, and others returned and felt limited in their career development, other graduates were able to secure opportunities in their rural communities that suited their interests and aspirations. This partly depended on their sector of work (for example, a number of these graduates were, broadly, seeking work in business related roles), on “luck” and on connections in the community. For some, graduates previous work experience was helpful in generating post-graduation opportunities in their communities:

I'm working at the NHS [island name] which is where I did my placement in my third year of uni. When I graduated I got in contact with a lady in the [name of] department, because that was kind of the area that I wanted to go into.

4.2.2. Relational frameworks

A second framework influencing graduate trajectories after graduation surrounds relationships. In line with previous research (Sage et al., 2013) returning home to live with parents was commonly discussed. This was particularly appealing to those who did not have a clear career direction, or a partner.

If I wasn't in a relationship at the moment and thinking about going to [name of city] I'd probably after uni be thinking about going back to [the islands] for a bit and living there for a while.

Given the evidence that the role of romantic relationships has been under-emphasised in graduate transition research (Finn, 2016), it is notable that alongside families, partners play a significant role in graduate destinations. In this research over half of the whole sample of graduates were living with partners one year after graduation (twelve students, or 55% of the sample). Of those in the islands, three were living with parents, three with partners, and two were living independently. This data demonstrates that although parental homes are important, returners in this study are as likely to be returning to live with partners as they are to live with parents.

Living with partners or parents is often identified as valuable for

saving on costs of accommodation. However, emotional considerations are also important:

We've been waiting so long for this long distance to end and for me to just suddenly decide that I'm going to go and do a masters right away would be ... I think next year seems like a better idea and it would give us a chance to actually be a normal couple as well for a little while.

In this quotation the potential tension between career frameworks and relational frameworks for young graduates is clear – and in practice many are involved in working out how to weigh up their different career and relationship priorities and needs, which might involve quite different spatial trajectories.

Similarly, although living with family can be valuable for saving costs, emotional connections are also important. Caring relationships, particularly with ageing grandparents or young nephews and nieces are a particularly important motivation for return. These are relationships where being physically close (in order to provide care) is highly valued, and where time is important:

I would always take my friends and family into consideration because I really love being close to them. And especially with my nieces and nephews growing up and things, I don't want to miss out on any of that.

Rather unsurprisingly then, intentions to return depend on how embedded graduate family networks are in the islands. Graduates with fewer family members in the islands were less likely to view a return as a possibility:

I have a very small family there's about seven people in my entire family. If I had more family I think I would move back.

Changes in relationships can also have implications for migration decisions over time. So, for example, for two graduates the likelihood of return decreased during the course of the research as their families either moved, or expressed an intention to move, from the islands. In one case an elderly family member with declining health was the primary reason for returning to the islands:

I found out my grannie had [a terminal illness] so I moved back to [the islands] for a year to be her personal carer.

Over time other graduates also describe other significant changes in relational frameworks that change their spatial intentions including relationship formation and relationship break-up. Break-ups with island-based partners can prompt moves elsewhere. Break-ups with partners on the mainland can prompt a return to the islands. Relationship formation with islanders can prompt a move home, or with those on the mainland, a move away. One returning graduate highlights the way that a relationship break-down combined with a work-opportunity in the islands prompted their return:

I had basically just split up with my boyfriend, was looking for an excuse to go home, [so I] jumped at the chance [of a work placement in the islands], and it was a great experience

Perhaps significantly even those participants who did not wish to return to the islands in the future typically identified that they may return to the islands, if necessary, for relational reasons:

I wouldn't say no [to going home], like definitely not because if I felt I needed to go back then I would, like if someone needed me to be there then I would.

4.3. Time-space context: "Settling down" and being "out of place"

As the previous sections demonstrate the interweaving dynamics of career and relationships inform graduate destinations. These dynamics can be somewhat unpredictable and create quite different experiences of

return.

Notably although graduates typically imagined 'settled' futures in the islands with a partner and a suitable job, for some graduates in this research this 'settling down' happened much more quickly than they imagine. By a year after graduation some students had returned to live with partners, had bought houses, and one was pregnant. One student reflects on their peer group:

I mean there's quite a few of them that have decided to come back as well and they're all ... I mean most of them are working in areas that they kind of studied in and they're a lot of them seem very settled, and a lot of them have bought houses and stuff and are having kids so

Alternatively for other students who had returned to the islands either without a clear career pathway, or without a settled relationship they could feel "out of place" and express an intention to move away again.

Being up here I'm never going to get where I want to be with my career, there's not the opportunities up here and I feel like, a lot of my friends as well are all married and having children and everything and I know that I'm definitely not going to be doing that any time soon [laughs] so I think everyone just seems a few years ahead of me, so I feel like moving back to [name of city], a lot of my friends that I was at uni with, they're all still there, which makes it extremely appealing because they're all kind of at the same level as what I am, just trying to get something with their degree and kind of get ahead with life, but ...

Here then this graduate is reflecting on a sense of different timelines in the island communities and in the cities and aligning their personal timeline (where they are with their career and their relationship) to these, suggesting that they are best placed in the city, whereas their friends are better placed in the islands.

4.4. A typology of returners

Drawing out the findings discussed above, it is possible to create a typology of returners based on career and relational frameworks and how these overlap (Fig. 1). This typology is intended to complement existing research, for example Stockdale's (2002a) typology of out-migrants from rural Scotland, and Cooke and Petersen's (2019) typology of island stayers and leavers. However this typology specifically focuses on young graduate returners, and identifies four categories of returner dependent on their position in relation to the two dimensions of career pathway and relationship pathway.

In terms of the career pathway, although 'satisfactory' and 'unsatisfactory' dimensions are identified, in practice it is important to note that this is not a clear binary, but rather options can feel more or less satisfactory depending on how graduates perceive their career options. Within the 'satisfactory' career pathway, graduates typically fall into the following categories.

1. **Planned returner (strategic)** Graduates who left their rural communities with a clear plan to return. Typically these graduates have studied a subject at university that provides a professional qualification in a role that they can undertake in their rural communities e.g. in healthcare or education. Whether and when they return depends on the availability of an appropriate job in their communities.
2. **Career returner (opportunist)** Graduates who did not hold clear plans to return, but who, by the time of graduation were open to returning and were able to secure an appropriate job. Typically these graduates have more open career intentions, and have studied subjects that could lead in a variety of career directions.

Within the relationship pathway, graduates report some variation depending on partner, and partner's intention – for example some

Career Pathway

		Unsatisfactory	Satisfactory
Relationship Pathway	Not in a relationship	<p>Unsettled: With no clear career pathway or romantic relationship, returning to the islands is primarily a return to a family home motivated by saving money. These graduates can feel unsettled and often express a desire to move back to the mainland.</p>	<p>Temporary – open: Having secured a satisfactory career opportunity in the islands but without a relationship, graduates can feel temporarily settled. Future horizons are typically relatively open, and for many depend on when and where they might meet a potential partner.</p>
	In a relationship	<p>Temporary – frustrated: Returning to the islands to live with a partner can appeal for emotional and practical reasons. However, if graduates do not have a satisfactory career opportunity, experiences can be marked by a sense of frustration or compromise.</p>	<p>Settled: Some graduates return to the islands within the first year of graduation to a partner and secure a suitable career opportunity. These graduates typically describe being settled in the islands.</p>

Fig. 1. A typology of Graduate Returners.

partners are felt to be very settled in the islands (meaning that graduates are more likely to stay) whereas other partners are less settled (and graduates may visualise futures which involve moving away from the islands with their partner). Family relationships are not specifically included in the relationship pathway, although it is important to note that it is an important factor for many, and for a small number of graduates family is a key reason for return particularly in circumstances of family ill-health or young children in the family. Both of these experiences are relatively time-bound with graduates imagining futures where these ties are less significant (for example, elderly relatives passing away, or children growing up). Where a graduate does not have a clear career pathway in the islands these family experiences can accentuate feelings of needing to compromise on career for sake of location; for those who are relatively settled in the islands, these family experiences can act as a further tie to the islands.

5. Discussion

The intersections between work and relationships in rural return migration have previously been explored in the work of Haartsen and Thissen (2014) and Rérat (2014b). However, this research adds to previous work by exploring how these dynamics emerge in the decision making of graduates immediately after graduation, highlighting the way they overlap and intertwine to create different experiences of return (shown in Fig. 1) The research also adds to the understandings of exactly how career and relationship dynamics are important in return migration.

In relation to the dynamics of career, although both Haartsen and Thissen (2014) and Rérat (2014b) indicate that specific career trajectories (e.g. in healthcare, education and other vocational routes) may be associated with return, this research identifies the complexity of these return pathways. Although vocational options appeal to those who wish to return in the future ('planned returners'), when and how return is possible is dependent on external factors such as professional requirements and the availability of work, and a wish of some students to develop additional confidence and skills rather than returning home immediately. These routes therefore appear to be something of a gamble

– allowing for a return, but with uncertainty about when, how, and if this will happen. A greater flexibility in possibilities for return is offered where graduates have more open career pathways, often broadly focused on business, and which do not require specific training routes. Where graduates have had relevant work experience in the islands, clear routes for return may be created. Therefore, this research highlights the importance of different occupational structures, and their timelines in structuring graduate mobilities. It also highlights how although 'good jobs' are often understood as important in attracting young people to rural areas (Cooke and Petersen, 2019; Crow, 2010; Jamieson and Groves, 2008) this terminology potentially overlooks the wide variety of occupational pathways, career interests and skills of different graduates, and how these have quite different spatial implications. Importantly in this research, some return graduates faced significant challenges if they were seeking to 'work their way up' in specific professional routes with limited possibilities in the islands.

The findings in this research about the importance of relational connections in return migration is also aligned to previous research (Haartsen and Thissen, 2014; Rérat, 2014b). However, a particular contribution of this research is the evidence that although many graduates return to their home communities, they are often not returning 'home' to parental homes but moving to be with partners. This is significant because where returning to parental homes can be experienced as a sort of going backwards, returning to live with partners is not constructed in the same way – often representing a form of progress (in relational terms), involving moving in together, and sometimes moving into home ownership. Where Finn (2016) has argued that romantic relationships need more consideration in graduate trajectories generally, this research highlights the importance of these relationships in understanding return migration to rural areas. A further important finding regarding relationships in this research is the significance of wider family, especially older and younger family members. Here the research highlights how some relationships (particularly caring relationships) require physical presence in a community and can be experienced as a significant motivation to return home.

In understanding experiences of return, dynamics of career and relationship cannot be understood in isolation, instead the way they

interrelate constructs quite different experiences of return. Where the experience of return is most positive, relational and career dynamics overlap – with young people moving home to “settle” in relationships with a partner, and in a job that they feel is aligned with their interests and needs. However, if graduates return and do not have suitable employment, or a relationship, then they can feel quite unsettled. There is resonance here with Lundqvist’s (2019) work which suggests that rural young people mostly aspire to a “good life”, often envisaged as being back in their rural communities (or a similar community) and consisting of “a comfortable and secure (family) life with sufficient steady income from an enjoyable job enabling professional and personal development” (p.9). It also suggests that although previous work identified three dimensions of rural belonging: to people, place and time (Cuervo and Wyn, 2014), a fourth dimension of ‘career’ could be added – in this research, having employment or being engaged in learning or another activity that was aligned to a graduate’s interests was an important element of feeling settled.

Importantly the intertwining of career and relational frameworks lends a degree of unpredictability to pathways as they are lived over time. In career dynamics spatial decisions are framed by what comes up, when, where, and how this intersects with a graduate’s position in their relationships, life-course and mobility intentions. Further, relationships change, and families are mobile, creating changing relational and spatial frameworks for graduates. Mobility and career decisions therefore develop *through* time, so that changing relational frameworks (where people are based, who is in their relational network) and career frameworks (where opportunities are coming up) could result in quite different spatial horizons. Therefore, it is important not to understand young people’s mobilities in isolation but to understand them as embedded within wider relational networks and employment and occupational structures.

Overall this research demonstrates that graduate return experiences are much more complex than the ‘success-failure’ dichotomy (Haartsen and Thissen, 2014) would suggest. In this research, arguably, a sense of “failure” in return was less apparent than perhaps a sense of frustration or compromise. In practice graduates described making difficult choices and facing dilemmas about the best ways to achieve a “settled” life, when the career and relational components of their trajectories potentially had quite different mobility implications. These experiences of compromise could reflect something of a rural penalty. Where young people in more urban or central locations may be able to live in their “home” communities and still access considerable training or employment opportunities, those living in rural areas may find this much more difficult (see also Milburn, 2009). Specifically, this research indicates a need for greater support for rural graduate returners who have not secured satisfactory career opportunities. Identifying how to support these graduates (potentially through career guidance, internships or placements, or funding for training and development) is important, not just for graduates themselves, but potentially because these young people represent a significant resource to rural and island communities whose skills, experience and knowledge may be currently under-utilised.

6. Conclusions

This research explores the experiences of rural return migration of recent graduates from Orkney and Shetland. The findings demonstrate that a small but significant proportion of graduates return almost immediately after graduation, however, the experiences of these graduates can vary considerably. Although as in previous research career and relationship motivations are key reasons for return, in this research it is how these dynamics interweave and interrelate which is identified as particularly important in constructing experiences of return. Where graduate return is accompanied by work that aligns with their career interests, and a partner, young people can feel very settled. Whereas other graduates returning to family homes without either of these can

feel relatively unsettled. Still others may return primarily for work or for relational reasons, and for these students experiences of compromise are common. These experiences have been summarised in a typology of graduate returners.

Focusing on graduate returners offers an important contribution to the rural return literature, which has often explored the intentions of return for young school leavers or return experiences of older adults. This research highlights that intentions to return (or not) do not always translate into actual pathways and that although ‘belonging’ is important in stimulating interests in return migration, it is not sufficient, with an individual’s career and relational frameworks providing different structures for mobility. By exploring the actual migration pathways of students and the dynamics behind these, specific implications can be drawn out for regional development interests. In particular this research suggests it is not just important to consider how best to *attract* returners, but also to consider how to best support returners who have already returned but who may struggle to access the resources (employment, training and education) that are necessary to allow them to feel “settled”.

Author statement

The author (Dr Rosie Alexander) confirms sole responsibility for the following: study conception and design, data collection, analysis and interpretation of results, and manuscript preparation.

Declaration of competing interest

None.

Data availability

The data that has been used is confidential.

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